

Development of pragmatic skills as an integral aspect in training young specialists

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Annotation

Nowadays pragmatic competence is so important. Lack of pragmatic competence may result to problem in communication such as miscommunication and misunderstanding. The utterances in miscommunication or misunderstanding may be considered rude insults. This is the main reason why students need to learn and to have the pragmatic competence to support their communication abilities. In order to teach that pragmatic competence to students, teacher, then, has to own this competence. He or she has to understand and aware of pragmatics knowledge and pragmatics competence.

Key words: pragmatics, communicative competence, main purpose of language teaching, pragmatic awareness, meaning in context.

Pragmatics and teaching languages cannot be separated since they shared one important aspect dealing with communication. Teaching language in general and teaching English in specific should involve an awareness of meaning in context. Teachers should be aware of their pragmatic competence to develop students' pragmatic awareness. The most important knowledge to be taught to students is the rules to use language for communication. Students are demanded to own the communication skills that can support them as the part of the society. Not only in the classroom, should students also be able to communicate effectively with language outside classroom or the real world. Therefore, English teaching is supposed to have the main role to carry out the main purpose of language teaching which is to develop students' communicative competence. One way can be done is to integrate English language teaching and pragmatics in the classroom. Teacher is required then to own pragmatic knowledge and competence in teaching English to his or her students.

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Pragmatic competence as a subcompetence within the framework of a foreign language communicative competence is the ability and willingness of a speaker to reproduce pragmatically literate statements, as well as to interpret the pragmatic intention of another speaker. Ignorance of pragmatic structures and principles can lead to misunderstandings in extreme cases. For future teachers and teachers of a foreign language, mastering pragmatic competence is important in the light of the correct transfer of knowledge about the discipline being taught.

Pragmatic competence is the ability of an individual to interpret and apply the rules for the construction of a statement (an opinion to be said, written), to apply statements (thoughts) for various communicative functions in accordance with the characteristics of communkants (participants in communication) and the social and cultural context of communication.

The component composition of pragmatic competence as a component of communicative competence in a foreign language includes the following elements:

a) social component (the ability to interpret the social contexts of communication and the social roles of communication participants; the ability to choose the socially acceptable style of communication);

B) socio-linguistic (sociolinguistic) component (ability to interpret a speech statement (social meanings, register variations and modality) to create a social urination/portrait of the interlocutor); ability to use the necessary language and speech tools to achieve the goal of communication in accordance with selected social roles));

C) socio-cultural component (the ability to interpret information received about the cultural aspect of the country of the native language and the intended (studied) language in intercultural interpersonal interaction conditions;

G) the speech component (the ability to interpret the choice of speech genres implemented by the interlocutor, the cohesiveness and coherence of a speech statement; the ability to select and implement speech communication in accordance with the rules for building speech communication to perform communicative tasks; d) the compensatory coponent (the ability to fill in spaces, spaces that are not understood in language and socio-cultural issues by

The formation of components of pragmatic competence is carried out on the basis of training to a number of pragmatic markers – to express the intended

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meaning/opinion, to organize a discourse, and to the sum of the lexical, grammatical and syntactic units of the language in order to organize an assessment relationship to the thought/statement being expressed. In the research work, four groups of markers are proposed: basic/basal (lexical, mixed, syntactic), explanatory, parallel (vocative, protest expression markers), and discussion/discursive (contrastive, elaborative, inferent, subject change markers).

In pedagogical circles, during the discussion of the problem of a competency approach, the word positivity is often mentioned, in traditional education, "the concept of competency does not add any novel principled approach", competency is a new interpretation of the concept already used in higher education institutions.

The historical roots of competency approach issues are reflected in the works of Eastern thinkers Abu Rayhan Beruniy, Abu Ali Ibn Sina, Abu Nasr Farabi, Abdullah Avlani. In our historical heritage, many opinions are expressed about the issues of the importance and meaning of the ideas of orientation to competency knowledge in the development of society.

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